

INFLUENCE OF SELF CONCEPT AND EMOTIONAL MATURITY ON LEADERSHIP BEHAVIOUR OF SECONDARY SCHOOLS HEADS IN KERALA, INDIA

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Abstract:

The present study tried to find out the influence of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity and their influence of interaction on Leadership Behaviour of secondary school Heads in Kerala in terms of their gender, age, experience and type of management of their school. The investigator approached 260 heads of the secondary schools throughout the Kerala to collect information regarding their Self Concept, Emotional Maturity and Leader Behaviour. The study found that the Self Concept of heads of secondary schools in Kerala does not have any significant influence on their Leadership Behavior for the total sample and subsamples of males, females, age group one, experience group one, experience group two and government schools. But the influence is significant in the case of age group two heads and the heads of aided secondary schools. The influence of Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behavior of heads for the total sample and subsamples of males, age group two, experience group one, experience group two and heads of government schools is significant whereas it is not significant in the case of females, age group one and heads of aided schools. The influence of interaction of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour is not significant for the total sample and all the subsamples other than male heads and it is significant in the case of male heads. The study also reveals that the Self Concept and Emotional Maturity jointly contribute significantly in Predicting Leadership Behaviour of heads of Secondary Schools in Kerala. The percentage of joint contribution of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity in predicting Leadership Behaviour is 13.31 percent. The individual contributions of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity in predicting Leadership Behaviour is 0.024 percent and 13.14 percent

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respectively. The study recommends for organizing various effective training programme for heads of the school to enhance their Self Concept, Emotional Maturity and Leadership Behaviour.

Keywords: self-concept, emotional maturity, leadership behaviour

1. Introduction

Self-Concept can be defined as the totality of a complex, organized, and dynamic system of learned beliefs, attitudes and opinions that each person holds to be true about his or her personal existence (Purkey, 1988). It is an organized collection of beliefs and self-perceptions about oneself. In other words it operates as basic schema. The self-provide a frame work that determines how human beings process information about their selves including motives, emotional status, self-evaluation and abilities. One has to work hard to protect his self-image from threatening information to maintain self-consistency and find excuses for any inconsistencies. Thus people tend to resist changes and to explain why the inconsistency with their self-concept. A self-schema is the sum of everything that a person remembers, knows and can image about him or herself. Self is the centre of a person's individuality as well as social world.

Emotional maturity represents capacity of an individual to manage and to check emotions, to evaluate others' emotional state and to persuade their judgment and actions. It implies controlling emotions rather than letting emotions get the better of. According to Smitson (1974) *"Emotional maturity is a process in which the personality is continuously striving for greater sense of emotional health, both intra-physically and intra-personally"*. Encyclopaedic Dictionary of Psychology (2001) defines *"Emotional maturity is an adult level of emotional control and expression as opposed to childish emotional behaviour"*.

Leadership is a boosting attribute that accelerates the performance of a group. A great leader can inspire the entire community by his thoughts and deeds. The effectiveness and efficiency of the leader influences and energize the performance of the institution, which will result optimum output in the field of education. Successful implementation of the educational programmes of every institution relies upon the leadership effectiveness of the classroom teachers, headmasters, supervisors, and administrators of concerned institutions. In a period of crisis and transition the position of the educational leader is more significant than at any other time. According to Bennis and Nanus (1985) *"Leadership seems to be the marshalling of skills processed by a majority but used by a minority. But it is something that can be learned by any one, taught to everyone, denied to no one"*.

2. Need and Significance of the Study

Leadership is a social phenomenon as well as critical factor in organizing successful institutions. In a group, the members who like to dominate often take advantage of all group situations and organize, channelize and direct the total energy of the group towards the achievement of group goals. Consequently they become leaders in the group. Thus a leader is one who is capable of exerting his influence on others to a much greater extent than others influence him. Even a small group may gain wonders with effective and motivated leadership. But a large group without an effective leader may achieve nothing. Like that, leadership of headmaster is a determining factor in the success of any programme in schools.. Heads of secondary schools in Kerala may lead scores of teaching and non-teaching staff in a school and the smooth functioning of the school depends on their leadership behaviour.

Like leadership, the concept of self is also a vital factor in ones' life. It determines success in one's life. It is the one's awareness on himself such as his personal strengths and limitations etc. awareness of the same will help a person to analyze and reason the things accordingly. Another important factor needed for a head of the institution is emotional maturity. Emotional maturity is the ability of a person to make effective adjustment with himself, members of his family, subordinates, society and so forth. The emotional maturity of secondary school heads is relevant in this context.

In this study, the investigator attempts to find out whether the self-concept and emotional maturity influences the leadership behaviour of heads of secondary schools in Kerala. A good leader must be aware of his self (abilities and inabilities) and be fledged with great degree of emotional maturity, because they must have to deal with a number of explosive situations. In such a situation, he must be able to keep his emotional health. So a leader without self-concept and emotional maturity may destroy the soul of a group or an organization or a school or a country. It is the need of the time to answer all the questions regarding this. Therefore, the study.

3. Review of Related Literature

The investigator has gone through many studies related to self-concept, Emotional maturity and Leadership Behaviour for the purpose of review of related literature. The summary of important studies is presented below.

Skariah (1994) studied creativity of teacher trainees' in relation to their self-concept, attitude towards teaching profession and success in teaching. He found that there is positive relationship between self-concept and success in teaching. The result

also shows that high teaching success group and high attitude towards teaching group are more creative than the other groups.

Ahmad, Ghazali, and Hassan (2011) studied the relationship between self-concept and ability to handle stress on academic achievement of student leaders in university Putra Malaysia. They found that there is no significant relationship between self-concept and academic achievement. The result also shows that there is no significant difference in the mean score of male and female leaders' self-concept.

Linda (2007) conducted study on effective leadership through Emotional Maturity. The study revealed that two basic factors, contribute to one's ability or inability to implement proper leadership techniques: first emotional intelligence, the cognitive understanding and acceptance of basic leadership principles and second the ability to implement those principles Emotional Maturity.

Keith (2009) explored the lived experiences of school principals with respect to their perceptions of the influence of emotional intelligence on their leadership. He found that principals have an effect on students' achievement and emotional intelligence effects the leadership performance on their school administration. Further he found that there is a positive relationship between the emotional intelligence and effective leadership.

Srilatha and Vanaja (2013) investigated the emotional maturity, social maturity and moral judgment of the student teachers of Guntur District. They found that gender, age, religion are influencing the emotional maturity among the teacher students while locale is not shown any influence on these variables. Emotional maturity of the student teacher is dependent on their marital status but social maturity and moral judgment are not. Family annual income does not have any impact on the student teachers emotional maturity, social maturity and moral judgment.

Finnigan (2012) conducted a study on Principal Leadership in Low-Performing Schools. This qualitative study of teachers in three low-performing elementary schools in Chicago revealed that transformational leadership behaviors were important to teacher motivation, affecting whether they believed that they could improve student performance as the accountability policy required. The findings suggest that principal leadership is critical to turning around low-performing schools. Implications include developing policies to hire principals with proven track records and increasing the capacity of current principals to ensure that they are able to support and motivate teachers in low-performing schools.

Vilkinas and Ladyshevsky (2012) conducted a study on leadership behaviour and effectiveness of university academic program directors that have responsibility for managing a program or course of study. The results lead to the conclusions that these

academic program directors were reasonably effective and had the ability to implement and further develop their leadership capabilities, even though they had no formal authority. In their role, these directors mainly focused on "*getting the job done*" and "*working with people*". At the same time, they placed less emphasis on monitoring their programs, maintaining networks and introducing changes, thereby putting their programs at risk.

Alsaedi and Male (2013) explored the attitudes of school principals in a Kuwaiti local authority towards the need for transformational leadership, the use of its behaviours, whether these school leaders are ready to behave in diverse ways or whether there are any barriers that prevent them from acting in such a manner. The findings of this study demonstrate that the participants agreed on the need for transformational leadership and had positive attitudes towards its behaviours. Although the participants identified some barriers to the application of this leadership style, the results indicated that the participants were generally ready to promote transformational leadership behaviours

Reviewing the above cited literature the investigator found that many studies related to self-concept, emotional maturity and leadership behavior were conducted among the school teachers, principals students etc. but there is no study was identifies where it solve the question of influence of self-concept and emotional maturity of heads of secondary schools particularly in the Kerala context. Hence by exploring the above stated related studies the investigator identified that a research gap and decided to study the "Influence of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour of Heads of Secondary Schools in Kerala". The review also helped the researcher to design the present study particularly in clarifying objectives; hypotheses as well as identifying suitable methodology.

4. Objectives of the Study

1. To study the influence of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity and their influence of interaction on Leadership Behaviour of heads of secondary schools in Kerala for the total sample and the relevant subsamples.
2. To find out the individual and combined contributions of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour of heads of secondary schools in Kerala for the total sample.

5. Hypotheses of the Study

1. There exist significant influence of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity and their influence of interaction on Leadership Behaviour of heads of secondary schools in Kerala for the total sample and the relevant subsamples.
2. There exist significant individual and combined contributions of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour of heads of secondary schools in Kerala for the total sample.

6. Methodology of the Study

The present study was indented to investigate the influence of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour of heads of secondary schools in Kerala. For the study the investigator collected the data from 130 heads of secondary schools in Kerala. Stratified random sampling technique was used for collection of data.

The self-version of Andrew and Halpin's Leadership Behaviour description questionnaire (LBDQ), Self Concept Scale by Pillai, Emotional Maturity Scale developed by Sing and Bargava were used for data collection purposes. Gender, age, experience as head and the type of management of their school were treated as subsamples of the study. Hence the heads were classified in to two, which are males and females on the basis of gender. They were also classified in to age group one (below 50 years) and age group two (50 years and above). Experience was another classificatory variable. Heads were classified accordingly to experience group one (below 5 years of experience as head) and experience group two (experience of five years and above as head). In the type of management two categories (government schools and aided schools) were identified. To find out the influence of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour the investigator categorized the independent variables such as Self Concept and Emotional Maturity into two levels, that is, high and low, the mean sores being the cut off scores between the levels.

The influence was identified by using 2X2 Factorial ANOVA. To predict the individual and joint contribution of independent variables on the dependent variable, multiple regression analysis was used. Multiple regression was done using enter method in which all independent variables were entered simultaneously. A regression equation was also developed to predict the dependent variable from select independent variables.

7. Results and Discussion

The investigator collected the data regarding the Self Concept, Emotional Maturity and Leadership Behaviour of the interested population to find out the objectives of the study. The result of the study is presented in two parts as given below. Part one shows the discussion regarding the influence of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity and their influence of interaction on Leadership Behaviour of heads of secondary schools for total sample as well as subsamples. Part second describes the individual as well as combined contribution of the Self Concept, Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour of the secondary school heads.

7.1 Part 1: Influence of Self-concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour of Secondary Schools Heads

The estimated data and respective discussion on the influence of independent variables such as self-concept and emotional maturity on dependent variable; that is leadership behaviour are presented below.

Table 1: Summary of 2X2 Factorial Design ANOVA of Leadership Behaviour with respect to Self Concept and Emotional Maturity for the Total Sample

Source of Variance	df	SS	MSS	F-Value	Level of Significance
Self-Concept	1	125.902	125.902	1.76	NS
Emotional Maturity	1	782.877	782.877	10.95	0.01
Self-Concept X Emotional Maturity	1	75.654	75.654	1.05	NS
Error	126	9004.872	71.467		

Table 1 show that the 'F' value for Self Concept is 1.76 which is not significant. It means that there is no significant influence of Self Concept on Leadership Behaviour for the total sample. From the Table it can also be seen that the 'F' value for Emotional Maturity is 10.95 which is significant at 0.01 level with df =1/126. It means that mean scores of Leadership Behaviour of secondary school heads belonging to low and high level of Emotional Maturity groups differ significantly. So, there is significant influence of Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour for the total sample.

The 'F' value for the influence of interaction of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour for the total sample is 1.05 which is not significant. It reveals that there exists no significant influence of interaction of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour of heads of secondary schools for the total sample.

Table 2: Summary of 2X2 Factorial Design ANOVA of Leadership Behaviour with respect to Self Concept and Emotional Maturity for Male Heads

Source of Variance	df	SS	MSS	F-Value	Level of Significance
Self-Concept	1	211.570	211.570	3.46	NS
Emotional Maturity	1	622.899	622.899	10.21	0.01
Self-Concept X Emotional Maturity	1	345.350	345.350	5.66	0.05
Error	74	4512.526	60.980		

Table 2 reveals that the 'F' value for Self Concept is 3.46 which is not significant. It means that there is no significant influence of Self Concept on Leadership Behaviour of male heads of secondary schools. From the Table it can also be seen that the 'F' value for Emotional Maturity is 10.21 which is significant at 0.01 level with df =1/74. It means that mean scores of Leadership Behaviour of male secondary school heads belonging to low and high level of Emotional Maturity groups differ significantly. So, there is significant influence of Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour of male heads of secondary schools.

The 'F' value for the interaction of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour for total sample is 5.66 which is significant at 0.05 level with df 1/74. It shows that the mean scores of Leadership Behaviour of Low and High Self Concept groups and Low and High Emotional Maturity groups differ significantly. It indicates that there exists significant influence of interaction of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour of male heads of secondary schools.

Table 3: Summary of 2X2 Factorial Design ANOVA of Leadership Behaviour with respect to Self Concept and Emotional Maturity for Female Heads

Source of Variance	df	SS	MSS	F-Value	Level of Significance
Self-Concept	1	0.021	0.021	0.00	NS
Emotional Maturity	1	274.013	274.013	3.25	NS
Self-Concept X Emotional Maturity	1	64.914	64.914	0.77	NS
Error	48	4038.333	84.132		

Table 3 exhibits that the 'F' value for Self Concept is 0.00. This means that there is no significant influence of Self Concept on Leadership Behaviour of female heads of secondary schools. The Table again shows that 'F' value for Emotional Maturity is 3.25 which is not significant. It means that there is no significant influence of Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour of female heads of secondary schools.

The 'F' value for the interaction of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour for female heads is 0.77 which is not significant. It reveals that

there exists no significant influence of interaction of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour of female heads of secondary schools.

Table 4: Summary of 2X2 Factorial Design ANOVA of Leadership Behaviour with respect to Self Concept and Emotional Maturity for Age Group One Heads

Source of Variance	df	SS	MSS	F-Value	Level of Significance
Self-Concept	1	48.688	48.688	0.69	NS
Emotional Maturity	1	159.717	159.717	2.27	NS
Self-Concept X Emotional Maturity	1	42.117	42.117	0.60	NS
Error	32	2245.833	70.182		

Table 4 shows that 'F' value for Self Concept is 0.69 which is not significant. It means that there is no significant influence of Self Concept on Leadership Behaviour of age group one secondary school heads. The table also reveals that the 'F' value for Emotional Maturity is 2.27 which is not significant. It means that there is no significant influence of Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour of age group one heads.

The 'F' value for the interaction of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour for age group one heads is 0.60 which is not significant. It reveals that there exists no significant influence of interaction of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour of heads of secondary schools belonging to age group one.

Table 5: Summary of 2X2 Factorial Design ANOVA of Leadership Behaviour with respect to Self Concept and Emotional Maturity for Age Group Two Heads

Source of Variance	df	SS	MSS	F-Value	Level of Significance
Self-Concept	1	288.635	288.635	4.013	0.05
Emotional Maturity	1	584.586	584.586	8.127	0.01
Self-Concept X Emotional Maturity	1	17.715	17.715	0.246	NS
Error	90	6473.846	71.932		

From Table 5 it is clear that the 'F' value for Self Concept is 4.01 which is significant at 0.05 level with df= 1/90 .It shows that the mean scores of Leadership Behaviour of Low and High Self Concept groups differ significantly. It reveals that there exists significant influence of Self Concept on Leadership Behaviour of heads of secondary schools from age group two that is heads below fifty years of age.

The Table again shows that the 'F' value for Emotional Maturity is 8.12 which is significant at 0.01 level with df= 1/90. It is evident that the mean scores of Leadership Behaviour of Low and High Emotional Maturity groups differ significantly. It indicates

that there exists significant influence of Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour of heads of secondary schools belonging to age group two.

The 'F' value for the interaction of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour for age group two is 0.24 which is not significant. It reveals that there exists no significant influence of interaction of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour of heads of secondary schools for age group two.

Table 6: Summary of 2X2 Factorial Design ANOVA of Leadership Behaviour with respect to Self Concept and Emotional Maturity for Experience Group One Heads

Source of Variance	df	SS	MSS	F-Value	Level of Significance
Self-Concept	1	50.804	50.804	0.66	NS
Emotional Maturity	1	355.545	355.545	4.61	0.05
Self-Concept X Emotional Maturity	1	125.658	125.658	1.63	NS
Error	93	7163.927	77.031		

Table 6 reveals that the 'F' value for Self Concept is 0.66 which is not significant. It means that there is no significant influence of Self Concept on Leadership Behaviour of experience group one secondary school heads. From the table 6 it can also be observed that the 'F' value for Emotional Maturity is 4.61 which is significant at 0.05 level with $df = 1/93$. It means that the mean scores of Leadership Behaviour of experience group one heads of secondary schools belonging to low and high level of Emotional Maturity groups differ significantly. So, there is significant influence of Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour for experience group one heads.

The 'F' value for the interaction of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour for experience group one is 1.63 which is not significant. It reveals that there exists no significant influence of interaction of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour of heads of secondary schools belonging to experience group one.

Table 7: Summary of 2X2 Factorial Design ANOVA of Leadership Behaviour with respect to Self Concept and Emotional Maturity for Experience Group Two Heads

Source of Variance	df	SS	MSS	F-Value	Level of Significance
Self-Concept	1	77.525	77.525	1.33	NS
Emotional Maturity	1	503.125	503.125	8.66	0.01
Self-Concept X Emotional Maturity	1	2.540	2.540	0.04	NS
Error	29	1684.639	58.091		

Table 7 depicts that the 'F' value for Self Concept is 1.33 which is not significant. It means that there is no significant influence of Self Concept on Leadership Behaviour for

experience group two secondary school heads. The table also shows that the 'F' value for Emotional Maturity is 8.66 which is significant at 0.01 level with $df = 1/29$. It means that mean scores of Leadership Behaviour of experience group two heads of secondary school belonging to low and high level of Emotional Maturity groups differ significantly. So, there is significant influence of Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour of experience group two heads.

The 'F' value for the interaction of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour for experience group two is 0.04 which is not significant. It reveals that there exists no significant influence of interaction of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour of heads of secondary schools of experience group two.

Table 8: Summary of 2X2 Factorial Design ANOVA of Leadership Behaviour with respect to Self Concept and Emotional Maturity for Government School Heads

Source of Variance	df	SS	MSS	F-Value	Level of Significance
Self-Concept	1	30.952	30.952	0.52	NS
Emotional Maturity	1	667.532	667.532	11.25	0.01
Self-Concept X Emotional Maturity	1	126.471	126.471	2.13	NS
Error	69	4092.539	59.312		

Table 8 exhibits that the 'F' value for Self Concept is 0.52 which is not significant. It means that there is no significant influence of Self Concept on Leadership Behaviour of heads of government secondary schools. From the Table it can also be observed that the 'F' value for Emotional Maturity is 11.25 which is significant at 0.01 level with $df = 1/69$. It means that the mean scores of Leadership Behaviour of government secondary school heads belonging to low and high level of Emotional Maturity groups differ significantly. So, there is significant influence of Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour for heads of government secondary schools.

The 'F' value for the interaction of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour for government schools heads is 2.13 which is not significant. It reveals that there exists no significant influence of interaction of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour of heads of government secondary schools.

Table 9: Summary of 2X2 Factorial Design ANOVA of Leadership Behaviour with respect to Self Concept and Emotional Maturity for Aided School Heads

Source of Variance	df	SS	MSS	F-Value	Level of Significance
Self-Concept	1	534.908	534.908	6.72	0.05
Emotional Maturity	1	123.520	123.520	1.55	NS
Self-Concept X Emotional Maturity	1	1.116	1.116	0.01	NS
Error	53	4218	79.599		

Table 9 exhibits that the 'F' value for Self Concept is 6.72 which is significant at 0.05 level with $df = 1/74$. It means that mean scores of Leadership Behaviour of heads of aided secondary school belonging to low and high level of Self Concept groups differ significantly. So, there is significant influence of Self Concept on Leadership Behaviour of heads of aided secondary schools. From the Table it can also be seen that the 'F' value for Emotional Maturity is 1.55 which is not significant. It means that there is no significant influence of Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour of heads of aided secondary schools.

The 'F' value for the interaction of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour for aided school heads is 0.014 which is not significant. It reveals that there exists no significant influence of interaction of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour of heads of aided secondary schools.

7.2 Part 2: Individual and Combined Contribution of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour of Secondary School Heads

Multiple Correlation and Regression Analysis using enter method was employed to find out the individual and joint contributions of Self Concept and Emotional maturity in predicting Leadership Behaviour of heads of secondary school. The data of inter-correlation of criterion variable with two predictor variables are given in Table 10.

Table 10: Correlation Matrix of Leadership Behaviour (Dependent Variable) and Self Concept and Emotional Maturity (Independent Variable)

Variables	Leadership Behaviour	Self-Concept	Emotional Maturity
Leadership Behaviour	1	0.01	0.36
Self-Concept	0.01	1	-0.03
Emotional Maturity	0.36	-0.03	1

Table 10 shows that the predictor variable Emotional Maturity obtained highest correlation coefficient ($r=0.36$) with the criterion variable. The correlation coefficient of Self Concept is ($r=0.01$). The model summary of multiple regression analysis is presented in Table 11.

Table 11: Model Summary of Multiple Correlation Coefficient for Leadership Behaviour (Dependent Variable) and Self Concept and Emotional Maturity (Independent Variable)

Predictors	R	R ²	Level of Significance
Self-Concept	0.365	0.133	0.01
Emotional Maturity			

Table 11 shows that the multiple correlation co-efficient is found to be 0.365 which is significant at 0.01 level. It means that Self Concept and Emotional Maturity jointly contribute significantly in Predicting Leadership Behaviour of heads of Secondary Schools in Kerala. Further 13.31 percentage of the variance in Leadership Behaviour of heads of secondary schools in Kerala is accounted for Self Concept and Emotional Maturity taken together. In order to know the individual contributions, the data were further analysed with the help of regression analysis and the results are presented in Table 12.

Table 12: Variable-wise Beta Coefficients, Percentage of Contribution and t Values in Predicting Leadership Behaviour

Predictors	Beta Coefficients	% of Contribution	t- Value	Level of Significance
Self-Concept	0.024	0.024	0.287	NS
Emotional Maturity	0.365	13.14	4.417	0.01

From Table 12 it is evident that beta Coefficient for Self Concept is 0.024 which is not significant while the beta coefficient of Emotional Maturity is 0.365 which is significant at 0.01 level. Further, the individual contributions of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity in predicting Leadership Behaviour is 0.024 percent and 13.14 percent respectively. Looking at the individual contribution, it can be said that Emotional Maturity contributes more to Leadership Behaviour while contribution of Self Concept is negligible. Thus Leadership Behaviour can be enhanced by improving their Emotional Maturity. For Predicting Leadership Behaviour from two predictor variables, viz Self Concept, Emotional Maturity the regression equation is calculated and presented as follows:

$$Y=0.016X_1+ 0.14X_2+94.21$$

Where

Y=Leadership Behaviour

X₁=Self Concept

X₂=Emotional Maturity

This equation can be used for predicting Leadership Behaviour of heads of secondary schools in Kerala using their scores of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity taken together.

8. Educational Implications

Based on the findings of the study the investigator put forward certain suggestions to the stakeholders which may improve the secondary education system.

As per the findings of the study it is suggested that special training programmes should be undertaken by the responsible department for heads of secondary schools to improve their leader efficacy as well as self-concept and emotional maturity. Self-awareness programmes and mental health training should be the compulsory part of professional development programme for the in service training. Performance based incentives may be introduced to those heads who brings radical and innovative changes in their schools.

It is also suggested to create an Indian Education Service/Kerala Education Service to groom academic administrators from qualified and experienced teachers with good leadership qualities. Academic administrators in the rank of heads of schools and above may be selected from this system which will definitely improve the education sector of the country.

9. Suggestions for Further Research

The investigator while working on his study has felt certain related areas for further research. They are the following.

- 1) Parallel studies may be conducted on heads of elementary and higher secondary schools
- 2) A qualitative study may be conducted to study the Leadership Behavior of secondary schools heads
- 3) Research may be conducted on the relationship between administrative skills of heads and the academic performance of the schools.
- 4) Job burden, stress and crisis management capacity of the secondary schools heads may be investigated
- 5) Self-esteem, social relation, community participation of heads of secondary schools may be studied
- 6) Studies may be conducted on managerial efficacy of secondary schools heads.

10. Conclusion

Kerala is a state where education and health sector are getting high priority from the government. Various innovative measures are undertaken by the government as well as NGOs to enhance the quality in educational sector. Each and every programme depends on the effective implementation of the projects. Behavior of the leader is crucial factor in this regard. Emotional maturity, self-concept are other important element which enhance the quality of one's personal as well as professional life. The present study was to find out the influence and contribution of self-concept and emotional maturity on Leadership Behaviour of heads of secondary school heads in Kerala. The result shows that the Self Concept of heads of secondary schools does not have any significant influence on the Leadership Behavior for the total sample as well as subsamples of males, females, age group one, experience group one, experience group two and government schools. But the influence is significant in the case of age group two heads and the heads of aided secondary schools. The influence of Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behavior of heads for the total sample and subsamples of males, age group two, experience group one, experience group two and heads of government schools is significant whereas it is not significant in the case of females, age group one and heads of aided schools. The influence of interaction of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity on Leadership Behaviour is not significant for the total sample and all the subsamples other than male heads and it is significant in the case of male heads. The multiple correlation co-efficient is 0.365 which is significant at 0.01 level which means that Self Concept and Emotional Maturity jointly contribute significantly in Predicting Leadership Behaviour of heads of Secondary Schools in Kerala. The percentage of joint contribution of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity in predicting Leadership Behaviour is 13.31 percent. The individual contributions of Self Concept and Emotional Maturity in predicting Leadership Behaviour is 0.024 percent and 13.14 percent respectively. The regression equation for predicting Leadership Behaviour from two predictor variables, viz Self Concept and Emotional Maturity is $Y=0.016X_1+0.14X_2+94.21$.

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